

The Influence of Discipline, Loyalty and Leadership on Work Productivity in the Secretariat of the Regional People's Representative Council of Selayar Islands District

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ABSTRACT

Raw materials have an important role in a company's production activities. Companies need to control raw material inventory because it affects the smooth production process. The purpose of this research is to find out whether the application of the EOQ method (Economic Order Quantity) can optimize raw material inventory costs at PT. Bumi Sarana Concrete (Kalla Block). The analytical method used is the EOQ method (Economic Order Quantity), total inventory costs, order frequency, safety stock and reorder point (Re Order Point). The results of this study indicate that using the EOQ method (Economic Order Quantity) can optimize raw material inventory costs. This is proven by the savings generated by the EOQ method. The results of the study show that there is a positive and significant influence of discipline, loyalty and leadership on work productivity. This is evidenced by the results of the test carried out by the t test by looking at the significant value of t count of $0.000 <$ from the significant level ($0.000 < 0.05$). Based on the results of the t test that has been carried out on the discipline variable (X1) on work productivity (Y) a value of $0.048 < 0.05$ is obtained, besides that it is known that the significant value of X1 to Y is 0.250. Based on the results of the t-test that has been carried out on the loyalty variable (X2) on work productivity (Y) the value is 0.039.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations cannot be separated from human factors as the driving force of the organization itself, so it is very important to manage human resources, as well as the organization itself. Employee behavior is basically related to various activities in the organization, because behavior reflects the involvement and existence of employees in the organization, therefore it is very important for organizations to be able to channel this behavior into capabilities that have positive meaning, especially in relation to organizational goals and objectives.

According to Hasibuan (2016: 193), discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms. According to Fahmi (2016: 75), discipline is the level of compliance and adherence to applicable rules as well as receiving sanctions or punishment if you violate the rules set out in that discipline.

Disciplinary problems are not only seen in terms of absenteeism, other problems related to the use of working time, compliance with regulations and compliance with technical instructions for carrying out work are part of preliminary observations and can be resolved preliminarily. Basically, discipline at the Selayar Islands Regency Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) Secretariat still needs to be improved. This is of course more true when formal research is carried out, as was the case in this study.

Regarding loyalty, observations at the Selayar Islands Regency DPRD Secretariat are still unclear, considering that DPRD members' activities are sometimes carried out outside the office and working hours, so that communication related to the secretariat also adapts to these activities. In fact, this is an interesting phenomenon, whether the implementation of working hours and activities outside the office is a form of loyalty or simply a work condition. To find out scientifically the relationship with the level of employee loyalty at the DPRD Secretariat of Selayar Islands Regency, a study needs to be carried out to draw scientific conclusions regarding the level of loyalty. Selayar Islands Regency DPRD Secretariat. A person trusts himself to be able to handle all his duties and responsibilities in other situations. This leadership quality inspires others to excel and achieve as one of the factors considered in concept development. (Hidayat, M., & Latief, F., 2018).

This leadership characteristic must also be possessed by every employee, including employees of the Selayar Islands Regency DPRD Secretariat. The author feels compelled to examine the nature of labor leadership because the quality of leadership is important, especially the societal paradigm, which the DPRD Secretariat views as representatives of the people, where workers must also be reflected as workers who have high social sensitivity. -Politics and social issues, the author's observations about the nature of leadership can be improved. The current phenomenon is that secretarial staff often work in the shadow of MPs and are therefore more likely to do what MPs ask of them. This is an interesting phenomenon because working in the shadows is a bad guide if not handled properly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. *Human Resource Management*

- a. Human Resource Management According to Mustamim (2020), human resource management refers to planning, organizing, leading and terminating employment relationships, developing remuneration, free integration, maintaining and terminating employment relationships with human resources to achieve individual, organizational and societal goals. Meanwhile, in Samsuni (2017), HR management is replaced by workforce management, namely placement, education, knowledge, regulations, development, workforce elements. Good and bad employees to achieve maximum efficiency and effectiveness depend on the organization.
- b. Personnel management functions in (Susan Eri, 2019), human resource management responsibilities include: Planning, Planning IE is an effective and efficient human resource plan for the company's needs to help achieve goals, planning is carried out by creating a staffing program. Organization IE Organizing is an activity where all employees are arranged into an organizational chart by creating division of work, work relationships, delegation of authority, integration and coordination because organizations are only a means to an end.

2. *Discipline*

- a. According to (Nuraini, 2017:106) Work discipline is respect, appreciation and compliance with applicable regulations, written and unwritten behavior, efficiency and avoidance of sanctions for violations of rules, violations of delegated duties and authority. Meanwhile, according to Hasibuan (2018: 193), discipline is the most important operational function of human resource management because the more disciplined employees are, the better their performance.
- b. Discipline is a sense of obedience and adherence to values that should be a responsibility, such as work duties in the office and employee presence at the company during agreed opening hours. Discipline is getting higher, employee efficiency is also increasing, so that employees are willing to work as best as possible to achieve company goals (Jepry & Mardika, 2020).

3. *Loyalty*

Riyanti's definition of loyalty (2017:6), says that employee loyalty is the determination and ability to follow with full awareness, responsibility, determination and ability which can be seen in daily attitudes and behavior in carrying out tasks. This opinion is interpreted in such a way that employee work loyalty arises internally and loyalty to the company where he works is based on his responsibilities and abilities. According to Hasibuan (2021:210), employee loyalty is the diversity of roles and members who give their thoughts and time to achieve organizational goals. Meanwhile, according to Suhendi (2017: 260), employee loyalty is shown by employee commitment to the

organization. Organizational commitment can consist of several factors, both organizational and individual.

4. Leadership

According to Sutrisno (2016: 122), leadership is a process of directing and influencing activities related to the tasks of group members. Meanwhile, according to Fahmi (2016: 122) leadership is a science that comprehensively examines how to direct, influence and supervise other people to carry out tasks in accordance with planned orders.

5. Work Productivity

According to Hasibuan (2016), labor productivity refers to a measure of production efficiency, namely the comparison of output and input, where input is often limited to labor input, while output is measured in physical units in the form of value.

6. Framework of Thought

Every organization is interested in productive human resources, management or organizational leaders always try to increase and maintain the productivity of the organization's employees.

Figure 1.1 Framework of Thought

1. Discipline influences productivity
2. Loyalty influences productivity
3. Leadership influences productivity

METHODOLOGY

In this research, a quantitative approach is used, the data source in this research uses primary data, namely questionnaires filled in by respondents, namely employees at the Selayar Regency Regional People's Representative Council Secretariat. And secondary data in this research is literature related to research in this research. The population and sample are 94 employees and uses data analysis methods, validation tests, reliability tests, multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Identity

This research was conducted on employees of the Selayar Islands Regency Regional People's Representative Council Secretariat. Data for this research was obtained using a questionnaire distributed directly to respondents at the Secretariat of the Regional People's Representative Council of Selayar Islands Regency.

- a. Respondent Characteristics: The respondents in this research were employees of the Selayar Islands Regency Regional People's Representative Council Secretariat. The following is a description of the respondent's identity consisting of the respondent's gender and age.

Tabel 1. Respondent Characteristics

No	Jenis Kelamin	Jumlah	Persentase
1	Pria	60	63,84%
2	Wanita	34	36,17%
Jumlah		94	100%

Sumber : SPSS 26 (Data diolah Tahun 2023)

Based on table 1.1, there are 94 respondents who are employees of the Selayar Islands Regency Regional People's Representative Council Secretariat, consisting of 60 employees or 63.84% male and 34 employees or 36.17% female. This research was dominated by male respondents totaling 60 employees or 63.84%.

- b. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Educat

Tabel 2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Educat

No	Jenis Kelamin	Jumlah	Persentase
1	SMA/Sederajat	2	2,13%
2	Diploma	21	22,34%
3	S1	43	45,75%
4	S2	23	24,47%
5	S3	5	5,32%
Jumlah		94	100%

Sumber : SPSS 26 (Data diolah Tahun 2023)

Based on table 2. There are 94 respondents who are employees of the Secretariat of the Regional People's Representative Council of Selayar Islands Regency consisting of 43 employees or 45.75% with bachelor's level education, high school/equivalent education level consisting of 2 employees or 2.13%, master's level consisting of 23 or 24.47%, S3 consists of 5 employees or 5.32% and Diploma education level consists of 21 employees or 22.34%. This research was dominated by respondents with a Bachelor's degree level of 43 employees or 45.75%.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

According to (Ghozali, 2016) this analysis aims to provide an overview or description of the data on variables seen from the average (mean), minimum, maximum and standard deviation values:

Tabel 3. Descriptive Statistics Results

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Kedisiplinan	94	3.38	5.00	4.2673	.44511
Loyalitas	94	3.50	5.00	4.3590	.35128
Kepemimpinan	94	3.20	5.00	4.3755	.40260
Produktivitas	94	3.42	5.00	4.4193	.36426
Valid N (listwise)	94				

Sumber: SPSS 26 (Data diolah Tahun 2023)

Based on the calculation results from the table above, the amount is known data or for each variable, namely 94 research samples. Explanation The variables will be described according to the data in table 1.3 as follows:

- a. Discipline: Has a minimum value of 3.38, a maximum value of 5, and a mean of 4.2673, while the standard deviation value shows a deviation of 0.44511.
- b. Loyalty: Has a minimum value of 3.50, a maximum value of 5 and a mean of 4.3590 with an affirmative answer, the standard value shows a deviation of 0.35128
- c. Leadership: Has a minimum value of 3.20, a maximum value of 5 and a mean of 4.3755 with an affirmative answer while there is a deviation of 0.40260
- d. Productivity: The minimum value is 3.42, the maximum value is 4.88 and the mean is 4.4193 indicating an affirmative answer

Reliability Test

Measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of a component or construct. This reliability test was carried out to test the consistency of respondents' answers to the questions given, using the Cronbach Alpha statistical method with a relevance of more than > 0.6 . Reliability test results.

Tabel 4. Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan
Kedisiplinan (X_1)	0,851	Reliabel
Loyalitas (X_2)	0,701	Reliabel
Kepemimpinan (X_3)	0,784	Reliabel
Produktivitas (Y)	0,797	Reliabel

Sumber : SPSS 26 (Data diolah Tahun 2023)

Table 4. Shows that the variables discipline, loyalty, leadership and productivity have Cronbach's alpha values greater than 0.6. This shows that the question items in this research are reliable. So that each question item used will be able to obtain consistent data and if the question is asked again, an answer will be obtained that is relatively the same as the previous answer.

Multiple Linear Analysis

Tabel 5. Linear Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.323	4.605		2.676	.009
	X1	.250	.125	.206	2.001	.048
	X2	.313	.149	.201	2.093	.039
	X3	.487	.095	.448	5.149	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

- The constant value is 12.323, the variable (productivity) is 12.323
- The Discipline of 0.250 shows that the discipline variable has a good relationship with the value of work productivity.
- Loyalty of 0.313 shows that the loyalty parameter has a good relationship with the value of work productivity.
- Leadership of 0.487 indicates that leadership parameters have a good relationship with the value of work productivity.

Hypothesis Testing

Tabel 6. Hypothesis Testing

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.705 ^a	.497	.480	3.15072
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1				
b. Dependent Variable: Y				

Based on table 6. There is an R square value of 0.497 or 49.7%, this shows that the productivity variable can be explained by the variables discipline, loyalty and leadership. amounting to 49.7% while the remaining amount was 58.3%.

t Test Results

Tabel 7. t Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.323	4.605		2.676	.009
	X1	.250	.125	.206	2.001	.048
	X2	.313	.149	.201	2.093	.039
	X3	.487	.095	.448	5.149	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Y						

Through t-test statistics consisting of discipline, loyalty and leadership, the influence on productivity can be partially determined

- a. First Hypothesis Testing (H1): Disiplin has a level of 0.048 which is smaller than 0.05. The b1 coefficient value is 0.250, the influence given is positive on the dependent. This means that H1 is accepted so it can be said that discipline has a positive and significant effect.
- b. Second Hypothesis Testing (H2): Loyalty has a significance of 0.039, which is smaller than 0.05. The b2 coefficient value is 0.313.
- c. Testing the Third Hypothesis (H3): The leadership variable has a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The coefficient b2 value of 0.487 indicates that the influence given is positive on the dependent variable. namely H2 is accepted so it can be said that leadership has a positive and significant effect on productivity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Discipline has a positive and significant effect on productivity. In this case, employee discipline plays a dominant, crucial and critical role in overall efforts to increase employee work productivity.
2. Loyalty has a positive and significant effect on productivity. Therefore, employee involvement in work is the extent to which a person does work and considers the level of perceived performance important for self-esteem. Employees with high levels of work involvement really like the type of work they do and really care about that type of work.
3. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on productivity. Leadership has a very important role in increasing employee work productivity. Where work productivity can be reviewed based on its level with respective benchmarks. The benchmark for work productivity can be seen from employee performance or work achievements.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so it will be carried out further on this topic. The Influence of Discipline, Loyalty and Leadership on Work Productivity in the Secretariat of the People's Representative Council of the Selayar Islands Regency with other variables including compensation variables, the provision of sanctions and inherent supervision in addition to the discipline variable.

REFERENCES

- Aspiyah, Mufti, and S. Martono. 2016. "Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Pelatihan pada Produktivitas Kerja." *Management Analysis Journal* 5(4):339-46.
- Digdowiseiso, K. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Ekonomi dan Bisnis*. In Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia (Vol. 1, Issue Metodologi Penelitian).
- Harahap, Dewi Suryani, and Hazmanan Khair. 2020. "Pengaruh Pencurian terhadap Masyarakat Sekitar." *Maneggio: Jurnal Ilmiah Magister Hukum* 2(1):69-88
- Mustamim. (2020). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (SDM) dalam meningkatkan kualitas pendidikan di SMA Darul Ulum*. *Education and Development*, 8(4), 275- 280.
- Pratama, Aris Yuda, Ismiasih, Tri Endar Suswatiningsih, and Siwi Istiana Dinarti. 2022. "Pengaruh Kepemimpinan terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan di Pusat Penelitian Kelapa Sawit Unit Marihat Sumatera Utara." *Agrifitia: Journal of Agribusiness Plantation* 2(1):22-33.

- Produktivitas, Terhadap, Karyawan Pada, P. T. Socfin, Indonesia Kebun, and Mata Pao. 2022. "1), 2) 1)2)." 4(2):1-15.
- Saleh, Abdul Rachman, and Hardi Utomo. 2018. "Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Motivasi Kerja, Etos Kerja dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Bagian Produksi di Pt. Inko Java Semarang." *Among Makarti* 11(1):28-50.
- Safitri Erma. (2013). Pengaruh Pelatihan dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Ilmiah Manajemen*, 1(4), 1044-1054.
- samsuni. (2017). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusi. *Ilmiah Keislaman Dan Kemasyarakatan*, 17(31), 115-116.
- Siti Nur Aisah. 2020. "Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan." *Bulletin of Management and Business* 1(2):42-50.
- Suryani, Popong, Yoyok Cahyono, and Berliana Dita Utami. 2020. "Pengaruh Motivasi dan Gaya Kepemimpinan terhadap Produktivitas Kerja pada Karyawan Bagian Produksi di PT Tuntex Garment Indonesia." *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research* 1(1):70-82.
- Susan Eri. (2019). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. *Manajemen pendidikan Islam*, 9(2), 952- 962
- Usman, Ismail. 2016. "Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan PT. Allo Jaya di Bontang." *EJournal Administrasi Bisnis* 4(3):911- 22
- Widayati, Fatriani, Happy Fitria, and Yessi Fitriani. 2020. "Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Loyalitas Kerja terhadap Kinerja Guru." *Journal of Education Research* 1(3):251-57.
- Wilianto, Hendry. 2019. "Pemetaan Loyalitas Karyawan PT. Mitra Tritunggal Sakti." *Agora* 7(1):121-31.
- Willianti. 2020. "Bab Ii Kajian Pustaka Bab Ii Kajian Pustaka 2.1." *Bab ii Kajian Pustaka 2.1* 12(2004):6-2